

TECHNOLOGY, SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

By

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ABSTRACT

The use of technology in supply chain management in recent times has brought about increase in customer and employee satisfaction as well as made the company remain competitive. The principal motive behind this study is to showcase the impact of technology on supply chain management of an organization towards the achievement of company's set goal. There is a general trend of retailers rushing into the acquisition and deployment of whatever technological application available without proper analysis of which is suitable for the ongoing digital transformation. This dissertation highlights the constraints and keys to a successful deployment of retail technologies and gives a quantitative analysis of the positive effect of retail technology on customers and staff satisfaction as well as achievement of set goals using a quantitative method (primary and secondary data). The methodological approach to the research questions involved the use of questionnaires and selected renowned online review agencies. This study reviews how Walmart (the case study) reflected when it invested in technology within the 2nd half of the last decade (2015 -2020) and also life experiences from shoppers with the deployment of technology. Based on these review the constraints to the deployment of retail technologies were within the spheres of high cost, technical bridges and social-political constructs. The keys were vested on the ability to critically reflect on a retail organizations position and how best it could deploy the retail technology now available to meet customers' ever-changing needs.

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CHAPTER 1 – INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background To Research

In a bid to cut cost of the retail industry viz supply chain cost, cost of building and maintaining retail facilities and staff remuneration, retail giants resort to using a combination of technology to attain better efficiency of supply chain and customer experience. Certain software such as Customer Relationship Management (CRM) technology, Hema QR Codes, Autonomous shopping carts, Automated checkout, digital price tags, self-checkout, retail mobile wallet, robot goods sorting, robotic delivery services etc. are being developed and deployed solely for the retail industry.

The rise of consumerism and its psychological reorientation has created a demand for easier, faster retailing. The quest for technologies that foster retail efficiency and better customer purchase experience has created a competitive atmosphere amongst retail giants. They are seemingly trying to outpace each other in the ‘retail technology race.

It is logical to analyze certain indices before deploying any retail technology because not all applications fit into all. What determines this measurement varies, like level of literacy, deployment cost, environment, state of mind, perception of previous deployment’s outcome, service delivery expectation as well as response time and much more. These parameters must be used while analyzing the feasibility of the deployment of any given technology in order to attain a successful

height.

Technology even though has been seen as problem solving agent is not without deployment hitches as highlighted by Walker (2018) that 25% of retailers are of the opinion that it makes transactions difficult while 75% believe that their experiences witnessed seamless engagement. Research work in this dissertation is about proving that the constraints if any in deployment for an effective outcome.

Using Walmart incorporation as a case study in this dissertation will clearly show how the company navigated towards achieving the success they display today in their deployment of technologies which was successfully carried out in their bid to take over their position from Amazon in early 2020 which was done seamlessly.

It's important to clarify that this research will work with the values maintained by proponents of the ideologies of technology utopianism and the liberal views of Social Construction of Technology (SCOT). While it is inarguable that technology has enhanced the strides made by the retail industry in solving supply chain problems and cut down operation cost, technology does not determine human action, but human actions shape technology. This research positions between these theories as it is geared towards analyzing the use of technological tools and the reorganization prior to a successful deployment while delving into the dynamics of successful retail technology deployment.

A strong motivation for this research also lies on the Structural theory of technology advocated by DeSanctis and Poole (1990) and Orlikowski (1992). The theory defines structures as rules and resources organized as properties of social systems employing a recursive notion of actions constrained and enabled by structures which are produced and reproduced by that action. However, in this theory, technology is not seen as a statue rather it examines the reaction of people towards the outcome of technological deployment in order to work with those towards making corrections if any for a seamless actualization of set company goals. Thus this research would examine without prejudice how each of the technology deployed within at Walmart has improved the lives of customers, the job satisfaction of Walmart staff, overall supply chain efficiency and reduction of the operations cost. This could be identified through consumer satisfaction indices, job satisfaction indices and supply chain efficiency calculation tools.

1.2 Problem Statement

The retail industry is riddled with several dilemmatic choices of technology to be deployed as a barrage of application of new scientific findings and technology breakthroughs are continuously

developed. The problem of choosing the optimum technology that at its best would not defeat the original goal of the company.

The responsiveness of these technologies and human adaptation to the new norms of a retail store is stringed to how these technologies impact positively to every stakeholder of the retail industry viz a viz costumers satisfaction, staff effectiveness and company's goals. The problem emerges as to when to draw a line between the technology being used as a tool and adapting to our ever developing lifestyle or we adapting to the technology. A positive impact of technology would be seen from the methods in which the technology improves situations for the better and not an improvement expressed by the wrong indices. For instance: a technology that reduces staff remuneration by replacing staff with robots would see a decrease in running cost even in the long run, but the customers may find it psychologically unpleasant as human interaction is brought to a halt.

Thus our definition of positive impact is largely determined by customer experience, supply chain efficiency and a seemingly general approach to questioning the interrelationship between the indices at which a retail organization would consider its deployment of technology as having a positive impact. This is in line with Patterson (2008), a proponent of the concept that supply chain efficiency is a cumulative expression of several indices within the supply chain and not by the word of a single individual or by a numerical value.

1.3 Aim Of The Research

This research is aimed at establishing a relationship between the use of technology in supply chain management and its positive impacts on a company's supply chain management. Using the case study of Walmart, the impacts include improved supply chain efficiency, workers satisfaction and company growth.

1.4 Research Objectives

The following are the specific objectives of this project:

- I. To Elucidate the different technologies deployed by Walmart in solving its supply Chain management problems considering its constraints and strength.
- II. To Analyze how a deployment of retail industry's cutting edge technology could impact positively on a retail organization's supply chain and by extension recommend possible methods of reorganization to accommodate a successful deployment of retail technology.

1.5 Research Questions

The important questions that this research will answer are as follows:

1. Are there constraints and keys to a successful deployment of the different retail technologies?
2. Does technology positively impact on the customers and staff satisfaction as well as achievement of set goal?

1.6 Structure of the Dissertation

This dissertation would include:

- I. An introduction to the different retail technology deployed by Walmart from 2015 and 2020.
- II. A literature review that surveys relevant sources of information on retail technology deployed by retail stores and either failed or did not pass the litmus test of retail success. It would also showcase Walmart's prescient as to which technology was suitable for their retail business, their weaknesses, strengths and past deployment failures.
- III. An explanation of methodology would be required: extricating the truths from myths by the use of transparent methods of research. Concise efforts would be made to use industry best practices and academic methods of research to present an unbiased result that would establish facts to the deployment of technology in the retail industry.
- IV. An overview of the results of this research
- V. A discussion of the results and their implications and finally
- VI. A conclusion and recommendation that shows what the research has contributed to knowledge of the retail industry about the impact of technology in their business.

CHAPTER 2 – LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent times there has been a growing need for dynamism and flexibility in supply chain management. The constantly evolving retail market, a shifting trend of consumerism and supply chain disrupting Covid-19 has shown us how technology could overcome seemingly overwhelming situations.

2.1 Technology and Supply Chain Management

Technology plays a vital role in expediting the speed of service delivery as well as keep the customers abreast of the service/product delivery schedule as a result technology effectively lowers cost of operation and working capital needs which ultimately results to customer satisfaction and consequent increase in sales revenue and achievement of set goal.

Supply Chain Management (SCM) is defined as the control of the movement of goods and services including the mode of transformation in order to take advantage of market place. With the emergence of a new way of shopping which is ecommerce, Supply Chain Management has become a vital concern for businesses. Given the ever increasing changes in the need of customers and technological advancement, the need for integrated supply chain management of companies cannot be overemphasized.

For companies to thrive in this world of global changes as evidenced in the recent outbreak of Covid-19, the need for digitalization of supply chain processes is obviously evident as will be shown in this dissertation. Chen and Paulraj (2004) described supply chain management (SCM), as a paradigm shift of modern business management as an integral part of planning and control of materials, services, and flow of information to and fro supplies to end users.

For many organizations, the use of information Technology in organizations viz a viz the supply chain has become paramount in the face of stiff competition Prashant, (2010), in his paper focused on the use of IT tools in Supply Chain Management (SCM). He emphasized the benefit of IT in assisting with restructuring the whole distribution for achieving higher rate of service and reduction of cost of supply chain management.

2.2 Supply Chain Management Efficiency and Responsiveness

Cost data gives more information as regards supply chain than any other source according to Schary and SkojttLarsen (2001) because Supply chain management is about cost reduction while at the same time improve the profitability of the company even as customers and employees satisfaction remains key. Efficiency is a combination of performance and cost in a way that will bring about actualization

of company set goal Patterson (2008).

In establishing the relationship between these variables, the article by Sanjay (2012) was very close to that. He recognized that management and human resources practices are as integral part of an organization which leads to the satisfactory performance of a company's supply chain management, employee well-being and derive recommendations that will guide the managers. In his analysis, his methodology talked about an expert in Delphi who carried out a study that first recognized the inherent effect of supply chain integration especially as regards human resource management (HRM) policies and practices and by using a survey of 228 supply chain professionals, hypotheses test that linked the performance of supply chain to non-traditional HR practices, training, and team organization was carried out. This study discovered some unique HR practices, such as flexible job descriptions and teamwork training that should be part of a successful supply chain integration. Results shows that flexible job descriptions, team organization, teamwork training, and performance metrics usage to determine benefits, are directly related to supply chain performance satisfaction. The flip side of this research is there was no direct display of consequent outcome as a result of technology integration. Upon this premise, this study shall present a formidable analysis, conclusion and recommendation that will stand the test of time even in the face of ever changing consumer need.

2.3 Walmart's Supply Chain

In analyzing Walmart's successful integration of technology to its supply chain management processes, Nguyen (2017) deduced that its successful technology deployment gives rise to its dominant present position as the giant retailer and emphasized existing issues in Walmart's supply chain. His interpretation was as a result of literature review on Walmart's integrated supply chain and the creation of Triple-A supply chain. This shows that it is of a necessity that Triple-A supply chain is built also for companies in the 21st century in order to achieve a formidable supply chain management. For this to be achieved, supply chain of companies must be redesigned to accommodate an integrated supply chain processes that has the ability to adapt, align and be agile to the environment such that the benefits will be widely seen and utilized effectively. The research authenticated that an integrated supply chain management should be adopted as pre condition for a company to improve its supply chain performance and achieve a formidable supply chain management processes which will make use of the improved technology. However this study is not without limitation which is the review of only literature.

However Guneskaren et al (2017), acknowledges the usefulness of large data and predictive analysis in the attainment of business value and performance of the company being highly utilized by Walmart Inc, Bradlow et al (2017), emphasis the importance of theory in guiding any systematic research for answers to retailing questions, as well as coordinating analysis. This study will deal more on streamlined primary and secondary data for more direct and accurate result for more transparent analysis that will prove the statement.

2.4 Technology And Walmart Supply Chain

Technology is defined as the application of practical sciences to industry or commerce according to Collins dictionary. This refers to methods, systems, and devices which are the result of scientific knowledge used for practical purposes.

Walmart became a supply chain leader by investing in technology. keeping to its objective of providing customers with low prices while saving money for other needs, Walmart has taken measures towards ensuring they are not found wanting and so over the years, it has embraced technology as the only means of having effective supply chain management processes by becoming an innovator in reducing cost, tracking and restocking the shelves as well as employees seamless way of transacting business and saving time. While doing this constantly and efficiently, Walmart became known as supply chain management master leader given the proven successful deployment of various processes and application.

Walmart, a traditional retail giant started breaking grounds in 2011 with its digital transformation taking another dimension from brick and mortar to clicks. Walmart is known for its technological innovations and so responds quickly to the urgent need for deployment of technologies in digital and supply chain technology

2.5 Review of Latest Technologies Deployed by Walmart

Walmart has proved to be responsive and adaptable with the outburst of the Covid-19 pandemic by the way it used technology is immediately adjust to the sudden change and ever changing needs of consumers. It quickly hired more staff and expanded its ecommerce in order to respond to the changing need of their customers. Displaying swift technological innovation readiness appears to be something that comes natural to Walmart as its track record has shown over the years and mostly in recent times where they used deployment of different technologies to overcome stringent issues they faced like the overwhelming show of capability they displayed during this pandemic.

Here are some technologies the company adopted within the past few years:

Predictive Analysis Software: This technology was deployed to solve the herculean tasks that face retail industries in their quest to analyze big data and be able to use the analyzed data to solve life challenging issues. With the invention of this software, retailers can now analyze consumer behavior from the available data from the past (Marr B. 2019)

Auto C: This technology is an independent floor cleaner, deployed to save employees hours of work for better efficiency.

Auto S: This technology is an independent shelf scanner that roams the aisles and scans items faster and accurately in order to track mislabeled, mispriced and the ones about to be out of stock to ensure immediate restocking. This helps Walmart be better organized and always stocked even as it is 3 times faster than human.

Walmart Fast Unloaders: This is a technology that uses automated conveyor belt to speed up unloading process for deliveries. This scans and sorts items as they are delivered from the trucks while taking into consideration their department and stated priority. This cuts down workers by half even as the job is done even much faster.

Walmart BOPIS (Buy online, pickup in-store): This technology facilitates the in store pickup of online orders. Consumers can place order online and retrieve it from a nearby store by scanning a unique barcode. This seamlessly makes in store pickup process very easy which will make consumers use Walmart BOPIS more often because of convenience.

These technologies make Walmart reduce cost and make employees more efficient in order to leverage on its brick and mortar. This task automation enables Walmart spend less on labor and deploy employees where they can make direct positive impact on consumers' shopping experiences.

ALPHABOT: Walmart presented its new technology known as Alphabot used for its grocery business in 2019. This technology enhances the picking, packing and delivering of groceries to online shoppers which aids speed in ordering with little or no issues- Thomas (2020)

Walmart Pay Smartphone App: This was introduced 2016 to make shopping faster and easier (seamlessly connecting online, mobile and stores) - Neil Ashe, president and CEO of Walmart Global e-commerce.

Scan & Go: Introduced by Walmart for Self-serve checkout. Scan & Go has the ability to Scan & Go using a smartphone which makes an already fast method of shopping even more convenient.

Eden Suite Of Apps: This technology uses sophisticated technologies like machine learning to create friendly applications in order monitor more effectively while at the same time care for fresh fruits and vegetables waiting to be moved from distribution centers to stores. - Musani (2018). In just 2019 this saved Walmart over \$2b.

2.5. Constraints of Deploying Technology to Supply Chain Processes

A study by Compuware on retail stakeholders reported that almost half of respondents (48%) emphasized that technological problems happen anywhere from a few times a week to every day while fifty-two percent said that the frequency of technological failures has been constant or rather increasing - Vanner (2013)

According to Sunol (2020) ‘,’ Retail industry is challenged by five technological issues; ranging from wireless disconnections due to network instability to Printing and scanning issues to Warehouse Management System to Transportation Management System problems due to software malfunctions to IT infrastructure problems and Lack of Technological Management know-how.

Some of these constraints revealed include; Lack of technical knowledge of staff, High cost of deployment and maintenance, Little or no historic I.T data to make informed technological investment decisions in order to discover differences if any in operations, and Lack of monitoring system to discover inadequacies before they occur.

2.6 Walmart Reviews of Secondary Data

Online reviews are a means of peering into the minds of consumers as well as get negative and positive feedback on a new product or a new development of things. Although most reviews tends to be from angry customers or very happy customers since normative services would not inspire anyone to make reviews as it is considered by some as a sheer waste of time. Yet reviews - especially with a high volume of respondents could enable a researcher peer into the mindset of consumers. In fact reviews from review companies are like questionnaires with more or less nonspecific questions whose analysis and inference still needs to be done. On the internet there are various forms of review companies and this research filtered the best based on its review strategy

and integrity.

Walmart reviews on the impact of the deployed technologies on customer and employee satisfaction as well as swift achievement of company set goals.

Consumeraffairs.com: review of 2,183 Walmart shoppers Nov.21, 2020. Rated 3.8 out of 5. Specifically talking about improvement in customer service after the introduction of retail technologies.

Influenster :2021 reviews of 4,314 Walmart online shoppers that got a rating of 4.4 out of 5. This was especially about the efficiency of shopping from Walmart after the introduction of retail technologies.

Sitejabber: Consumer rating of 3.5 from 4,185 Walmart shoppers who were satisfied with the significant improvement in Walmart services after the introduction of technology which shows in their delivery services.

AmbitionBox: Reviews by 619 Walmart Employees rated Walmart 4.2 out of 5 based on their satisfaction with the application of retail technologies.

An Insider review: Feb 21, 2019 based on digital transformation which has addressed the out of stock issue such that once you place an order, You are sure to receive it.

Indeed: Rated 3.5 · from 214,173 Walmart employee reviews based on technology effective improvement.

Glass door: This is one of the largest online review company on the internet. Their review is more widespread as it covers many aspects including consumer, employee and employer review. With over 58,982 reviews Walmart is given a 3.3 star rating out of 5 stars. The review is continuous. Glassdoor (2020)

Site Jabber: Another online review company is Site Jabber, it has a large spread of consumer metrics and delivers better data. Of the 4184 reviews taking between 2016 to 2020 the company had a 3.47 star rating out of 5 stars. This indicated that most consumers are generally satisfied with their purchases. About 1929 customers out of 4,184 gave Walmart a 5 star and 1088 gave a 1 star. Consumers satisfied mostly mention free shipping as an incentive, great prices and local store option on the other hand of the 39 respondents who specifically mentioned delivery only 2 gave positive review. Generally, delivery had negative reviews as they complain of error in logistics. The review is

continuous. SiteJabber (2020)

The charts below show the trends in ratings. The trends could be explained by the general acceptance of Walmart experience until Amazon took over the scene with its technology driven retail process. Walmart leveled the slope by 2019 and 2020 and hopefully would perform better as it heavily invested in technology.

Consumer Affairs: This is another source of vetted consumer review of companies.

Based on 2,198 ratings submitted between 2019 and 2020, Walmart had a 4 star rating out of 5 stars. Generally the ratings were between 3 and 5 stars and a little percentage giving 1 or 2 star rating. Consumer Affairs (2020)

Indeed: This company is one of the largest online review companies as it does more than review. With a large number of respondents (213 323), Walmart got a 3.5 star rating out of 5 stars. Although indeed is mostly flooded with employees the rating gives an insight as to the current satisfaction of workers as an indirect consequence of leveraging on technology to improve service delivery. Indeed (2020)

More specific metrics can be gotten from specific reviews on:

Customer Loyalty: Between January 1 to February 28, 2019, Inmarket - a digital advertising company made a research on customer loyalty. They gave loyalty scores based on represented device visitation - a device that trails how many times a customer visits a certain path. Walmart came up top with a loyalty score of 2.42 out of 4. The InMarket spokesperson described the process, explaining that visits to the stores on the list ranges from "the tens of thousands for the smaller chains, to well over a million for the largest chains." Cain, A (2019).

Company growth: Kee'fe, B. O (2019) reported that in August 2019 Walmart had its 20th straight quarter of U.S. same-store sales growth and a 37% gain in U.S. e-commerce sales. He further described this growth as a result of the investments the company made into in higher wages and benefits for his workforce as well as technology to boost the speed of sales.

Figure 2.6 Walmart Site Jabber review trends - Source SiteJabber (2020)

2.7 How Technology Positively Affect Customer Experiences

The high use of technology in recent times and the obvious improvement it has brought to business owners and shoppers has made it clear that it has become a tool necessary for retail businesses to thrive and so should be adopted in their supply chain processes if they have to grow and remain in business. According to Faroudi et al (2017), the influence of smart technology usage, combined with behavioral intention of the customer, on the dynamics and experience of customers was not acknowledged by the academic literature. The research rather used explanatory approach at the early stage to research this fact in a typical retail setting which was done using the survey of 330 consumers shopping in London, United Kingdom. This research proved that there is a positive correlation between consumer satisfaction and technology deployment.

2.7.1 How Technology Positively Affect Human Resource Experiences

Research has shown that technological advancement has come to stay and so will continue to have a dramatic effect on work processes and procedures, but it is difficult to distinguish between the hype given to it and the actual impacts. A study by Parry and Battista (2019) examined the evidence

backing fact behind the positive impact of emerging technologies on work and the role of the human resource (HR) function in helping employees and organizations to navigate these changes. The evident review of the study and the discussion herein suggests that emerging technologies such as AI, robotics, VR and AR, digital technologies, wearables and block chain have the potential to affect work and employees significantly. The significant impact of this, is largely dependent on developments of the technologies themselves and the organizations willingness to adopt and deploy them. These reviews show that the **HR function has a key role to play** in assisting the employees through the changes in the work regarding to skills development, work organization and mental health. The key activities involved in HRM such as to support managers and employees in carrying about their daily work (CEB, 2018), are capable of changing the role of the HR function by making it even more important as both the potential benefits and risks of emerging technologies for employees development. The ability of the HR function to successfully undertake this role depends largely on the development of their skills as

well as their understanding of technologies and their implications. According to Jesuthasan (2017), "digital engagement sustenance in the future workplace has become very key aspect of the HR functions. The actual HR function accommodates the development and full support of employees in order to improve on their growth and well-being, as well as the sustainability of the organization, against the backdrop of this technological advancement.

In 2015, Barley reiterated that technologies trigger change by altering workers' non -relational roles thereby affecting their daily tasks. Such changes may lead to changes in the way and manner they interact amongst themselves in a bid to carrying out their duties like robots seen as coworkers. This can affect the social network which will mean that technology has altered their work system. Therefore Changes in functions of relations are key to changes in work systems. Ethnography being the role-based studies of how technologies alter work systems would usually be involved. This gives answers to who interacts with whom, and about what, but not how their relationships are enacted (Barley 2015). researchers document repetitive patterns of encounters in order to know how workers react given their different job functions. This method is known as dramaturgical analysis (Goffman 1983) and it tries to find out how technology affects the functions of relations within the work space where they live. The combination of dramaturgical analysis and role theory gives researchers room to holistically address social and material features of technology-based changes in work processes.

2.7.2 How Technology Positively Impacts On The Sales Revenue Of A Company (Walmart As A Case Study)

Top 10 US Companies, Ranked by Retail Ecommerce Sales, 2017-2019			
<i>billions, % change and % of total retail ecommerce sales</i>			
	2017	2018	2019
1. Amazon	\$190.51	\$234.61	\$282.52
—% change	28.9%	23.1%	20.4%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	42.0%	44.8%	47.0%
2. eBay	\$34.45	\$35.63	\$36.34
—% change	5.8%	3.4%	2.0%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	7.6%	6.8%	6.1%
3. Walmart	\$15.04	\$20.95	\$27.81
—% change	47.2%	39.3%	32.7%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	3.3%	4.0%	4.6%
4. Apple	\$17.12	\$19.92	\$22.93
—% change	35.9%	16.3%	15.1%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	3.8%	3.8%	3.8%
5. The Home Depot	\$6.48	\$8.18	\$10.07
—% change	22.0%	26.3%	23.0%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	1.4%	1.6%	1.7%
6. Best Buy	\$5.89	\$6.61	\$7.53
—% change	21.8%	12.2%	13.9%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	1.3%	1.3%	1.3%
7. Macy's	\$5.83	\$6.60	\$7.44
—% change	14.1%	13.3%	12.7%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	1.3%	1.3%	1.2%
8. Qurate Retail Group	\$3.42	\$6.49	\$7.54
—% change	7.1%	89.7%	16.1%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	0.8%	1.2%	1.3%
9. Costco	\$4.58	\$6.01	\$7.71
—% change	26.3%	31.3%	28.4%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	1.0%	1.1%	1.3%
10. Wayfair	\$4.08	\$5.76	\$7.68
—% change	36.1%	41.4%	33.3%
—% of total retail ecommerce sales	0.9%	1.1%	1.3%
Total	\$287.40	\$350.77	\$417.57

Note: represents the gross value of products or services ordered via each company's website (browser or app), regardless of the method of payment or fulfillment; excludes travel and event tickets
Source: eMarketer, Feb 2019

245260 www.eMarketer.com

Fig 2.7 - Retail E-commerce sales Ranking (2017 - 2019) - Source - E-marketer (2019)

With the statistics shown in figure 2.1, Amazon took the first position because of the high technological innovations it introduced into their large online presence in the global market and a more successful mobile app and Amazon Prime loyalty program which increased the speed of service delivery.

According to fortune, Walmart invested so much in technology in 2015 in order to remain relevant in that space this made Walmart sales in ecommerce sales go up by 12% to \$13.7 billion while Amazon sales grew by 20% to \$107 billion. Walmart improved on its mobile app which seamlessly allowed

online grocery orders to pick up from nearby store as soon as order is placed. This was done in 2016.

Walmart launched its own Walmart Pay mobile payment system and its own open-sourced cloud service in 2016 December which is an option to Amazon Web Services.

According to com Score, despite Walmart constant technological upgrade in their website and mobile app, Amazon still took the lead in the use of website and mobile app for the year. Walmart introduced SHIPPING PASS, an alternative to Amazon prime which offers 3 day delivery at the cost of \$50 per annum which is half of what Amazon charges for a 2 day delivery using prime.

According to Neil Ashe, the technological investments improved their customer satisfaction experience during the fourth quarter across digital and physical which increased sales tremendously around the world. “We made great progress on our priorities, including our global technology platform, next generation fulfillment network and the integration of digital and physical. “said Ashe and Walmart will continue to boost its ecommerce sales growth in this technological age.

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Walmart improved on its mobile app which seamlessly allowed online grocery orders to pick up from nearby store as soon as order is placed. This was done in 2016. Walmart launched its own Walmart Pay mobile payment system and its own open-sourced cloud service in 2016 December which is an option to Amazon Web Services.

According to com Score, Despite Walmart constant technological upgrade in their website and mobile app, Amazon still took the lead in the use of website and mobile app for the year. Walmart introduced SHIPPING PASS, an alternative to Amazon prime which offers 3 day delivery at the cost of \$50 per annum which is half of what Amazon charges for a 2 day delivery using prime.

According to Neil Ashe, the technological investments improved their customer satisfaction experience during the fourth quarter across digital and physical which increased sales tremendously around the world. “We made great progress on our priorities, including our global technology platform, next generation fulfillment network and the integration of digital and physical. “Said Ashe

and Walmart will continue to boost its ecommerce sales growth in this technological age.

The trend of consumer change witnessed during the pandemic gave rise to the latest US ecommerce sales increase for Walmart shown in the head to head competition amongst the giants Walmart and Amazon across digital and physical retail sales platform.

Walmart resilience in meeting up and overtaking Amazon in order to remain the giant retail is evident in their investment in technology which has brought them this far and they developed their own information Technology department and recruited highly sophisticated experts in technology and invested heavily in them, this has put their developers on their toes in order to meet up with the ecommerce challenge Amazon has given them. According to Ashe, "This has made our in house developers to be significantly much more productive which helps them develop product enhancement much faster"

Fig 2.7.1 - Retail E-commerce sales Ranking (2017 - 2019) - Source - E-marketer (2019)

This technological impact brought about what we see on the global sales ranking a shown in fig 4 where Walmart took the lead with a wide margin and are still working technologically tirelessly in their effort to sustain their number position which gave them the title retail giant and this was only possible because of their technological deployment expressly.

Figure 2.7. - World's Largest Retailer - Source - Statista (2020)

Figure 2.8. - Walmart U.S e-commerce sales - Source - GeekWire (2020)

CHAPTER 3 — RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Research is a process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting data in order to understand a fact (Leedy & Ormrod, 2001) that has standard procedures and approaches. Saunders research onion is one of these approaches. It dictates the order in which a research can be done. It provides an effective progression through which a research methodology can be done. The usefulness of Saunders research onion lies in its adaptability.(Bryman, 2012). Saunders et al. (2012) emphasized that while using a research onion, the researcher must go from the outer layer to the inner layer.

Figure 3.0 - Saunders Onion - [Source -Thesismind (2019)]

Creswell (2002) noted that quantitative research is the process of collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and writing the results of a study, while qualitative research is the approach to data collection, analysis, and report writing differing from the traditional, quantitative approaches. Creswell (1998) insists that the procedural format of writing a research involves the use of research questions that explore the meaning of the experience, conducting the interviews, analyzing the data to find the meaning, and ending with a report that makes it clear for readers to understand the essential structure of the experience. The study collects data that leads to discovering a common subject matter.

3.2 Research Approaches

Three approaches are in existence thus quantitative, qualitative and pragmatism Grover (2015).

Quantitative approach (Positivism) is known to give much emphasis on absolute truth to be found experimentally using exact measurements. Positivism is well suited to physical sciences and business research. It deductions has no possibility of changing with time and context as physical parameters remain same. This uses closed ended approach.

Qualitative approach (Constructivist): This approach is quite individualistic as it is believed that: every individual has his own notion or reality about objects and subjects and so the researcher is guided based on this fact. This uses open ended approach which gives freedom to respondents allowing the respondent to construct its own thoughts as he deems fit. This is only good for research that has definite numbers.

Pragmatism (Mixed research approach): This was borne out of the belief that research methods is not fit for marginalized individuals and as such the research methods should be made to fit the case study or environment.

3.3 Research Onion

From Saunders onion in figure 3.1, this research hopes to align itself to the following procedural pattern:

3.3.1 Interpretivism (Research Philosophy) -

Because the values and beliefs of researchers cannot fully be removed from their inquiry, interpretivists believe research on human beings by human beings cannot yield objective results. Thus, rather than seek an objective perspective, interpretivists look for meaning in the subjective experiences of individuals who engage in social interaction. This approach is about data collection such as interviews and observations. This only makes meaning towards the end of the research process- Saunders (2012). The main variation of interpretivism is the act of seeking to understand the world by directly experiencing the fact "Littlejohn and Foss (2009).

3.3.2 Inductive reasoning (Research Approach)

According to Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (2018) - “an inductive logic is a logic that has evidential support”. This research which will work on inductive reasoning will apply data towards identifying findings outlined by its **core objectives**.

3.3.3 Case study (research strategy)

White et al. (2013) described case studies as that which provides a means for exposing and bringing out practical principles and recommend methods for shaping and speeding up progress in solving real world problems. They inform sophisticated theories such as those linked with complicated systems where people are seen as part of the system to be devised, developed, fielded, and operated; or abiding systems earmarked for improvement. The authors have advocated that case studies are important and a valuable means for understanding what works and doesn't work in a real life situation while addressing the most difficult, challenging problems.

3.3.4 Time horizon

There are two time horizons in conducting a research, most especially with a case study in view - cross-sectional and longitudinal time horizons.

The longitudinal time horizon refers to an extended study carried out periodically, with each time using numerous participants or samples with the same questions. This research is accustomed to the cross-sectional time horizon, which is the single point view of an aspect of a system. It is situational in nature as it describes the current state or accumulated impact of a subject of a system. In the case of this research work a cross-sectional view is necessary as it would showcase the accumulated effect of technology on the supply chain of retail companies as well as give a futuristic prediction of retail structure in the event of deployment of technology in the supply chain of retail industry.

3.3.5 Data collection methods: The method of this research is the data collection which is quite diverse in nature but for the purpose of accuracy, cost constraints, simplicity and avoidance of reinventing the wheel, the use of secondary data from authentic company review platforms would be analyzed as well as primary data in the nature of questionnaire. Given the nature of this research, secondary data would not be sufficient and should go with observations and questionnaires. According to Cacciattolo (2015), secondary data carries out a line-up of research objectives by addressing questions that were not considered in the original analysis. This is made possible by the fact that researchers are directed by secondary data in designing primary research as well as make

provision for the basis for comparison of the primary data analysis results and . secondary data analysis is used to analyze different analytical approach that changes the conclusions made available by original analysis - (Bryman, 2004). The effectiveness of questionnaires has been argued over the years yet questionnaires are often used as methods of scientific research and surveys, especially in education and in the business world and same will be used for the purposes of this study.

Figure 3.3 - Research Onion for this research

3.4. Questionnaire Design

According to Mcleod (2018), questionnaires are research instruments comprising of series of questions for the sole purpose of gathering information from respondents - a pseudo written interview. One of the obvious advantages of questionnaires is that data can be collected relatively quickly especially for large populations where interviews are impractical. In this dissertation the sample size is moderate and the spread across the population category is moderate.

Questionnaire is divided into two; quantitative and qualitative method depending on the nature of the questions. Closed-ended questions with multiple choice answer options are analyzed using quantitative method which may involve pie-chart, bar-charts and percentages while answers to open-ended questions which involve discussions and critical analyses without the using numbers and calculations are analyzed using qualitative method.

The usefulness of questionnaire is basically the speed in collection of data, low or no cost and high level of objectivity compared to other types of primary data collection available nevertheless it lacks the freedom of answers to additional relevant questions which may not have been among the stated questions thereby making some pressing questions in the mind of the respondents not to be answered.

3.4.1 Construction of Questionnaire For The Survey

The questionnaire for this survey (See Appendix, A1) is constructed by using the Quantitative approach (Positivism) which is known to lay more emphasis on absolute fact to be found experimentally using exact measurements by collection of data, analyzing them and interpreting them for informed conclusion and recommendation for references and future adoption in a bid for achievement in the achievement of company goal. Using this quantitative method allows the respondents to indicate their extent of agreement with the topic or disagreement. In this case, analysis are based on periodic shopping experiences like daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly shopping experiences was used, and also 4 point question scale was applied where the respondents were asked to pick their stand given the different options made available: “Strongly Agree, Slightly Agree, Strongly Disagree and Slightly Disagree”. These answer points were placed from 1-4 in order.

It is therefore imperative to acknowledge the fact that all the questions used here were made in positive sense in order to reflect the positive impact of technology on retail business which means that if they agree mostly with the positive impact of technology on retail business, it then confirms the positive effects demonstrated by the respondents but if they disagree then means that the real responses did not confirm the claim of positive impact of technology on retail businesses as observed by respondents. The questionnaire that has 20 questions is divided into parts, keeping in view the research questions and hypothesis so that the responses about different hypothesis could be collected separately.

Before the questionnaire was distributed, there was a small pilot study carried out in Nigeria where 30 copies of the questionnaire were distributed randomly and responses were collected and analyzed from the answers, this was to make sure that the questionnaire is understood clearly by the intended participants. The questionnaire was then distributed online to male and female of ages 20 and above from where responses were got from different parts of the world like the USA, South Africa, Canada, Nigeria, etc. The overall response of the shoppers’ towards the survey questionnaire was encouraging. As the questionnaire consists of close ended questions and the respondents were not asked to write too much regarding their experiences and opinions, so they found it easy and convenient filling the questionnaire in as short a time as 2 minutes. Given the pandemic, the questionnaire was restricted to online audiences who are usually skeptical with clicking links, and so the extra mile was taken to convince as many as 88 respondents in order to have a reasonable number to analyze and measure accurately.

3.5 Data Collection and Analysis

The sample size is 88 persons from around the world about 31.8 % resides in America while 19.3% in Canada. The sample is also gender tilted as 71.5% of respondents are females. This does not affect the quality of the response as 65% of family primary shoppers according to Statista (2018) are females. A good percentage - 84 % of respondents are above 30 years of age. This should not affect the quality of the research as Generation Z are not a large percentage of Walmart shoppers. According to PMNTS (2016), the average Walmart shopper is 50 years old.

In order to guide the research into a range of answers as clearly defined by the nature of the research questions, the questionnaires would be the closed ended type. The questionnaires ask general questions to ascertain the peculiarity of the respondents and in what category the respondents belong. For simplicity and ease of filling questionnaire, the questions are with multiple choice answers. The options selected for each question are analyzed using quantitative methods involving pie-charts, bar-charts and percentage.

3.5.1 Basis for Data Analysis

As soon as the responses from questionnaires were received from the respondents, their responses were analyzed for each of the question after which the analysis was made. For example where there are more responses for “Strongly Agree” (i.e. number 1) it means that more respondents agreed with the given statements. In order to get clearer picture of the responses, strongly agree are combined with slightly agree while strongly disagree with slightly disagree for better interpretation.

3.5.2 Analysis of Data

The filled questionnaires were put together for the sake of analyzing the result of the survey. This was done section by section as shown above so that each section will clearly show the trend of issues being discussed without any form of confusion or ambiguity. For instance the second section questions is about the overall deployment of retail technologies by Walmart and the ease of deployment, whereas the third section speaks about the positive impact of the deployed retail technologies by Walmart on costumers and staff as well as company’s achievement of goals. The results are analyzed individually for each section so that the research questions would be addressed viz a viz data gathered from each section and the same data used for hypothesis test. Finally, all the results of the survey are analyzed in order to form an opinion regarding the overall impact of technologies on retail businesses using

Walmart as a case study.

Data gathering for section 1

This section deals with the personal information of the respondent in order to showcase the reality of the data being collected even as they were assured of confidentiality of information submitted. The questions were 4 and the data was gathered from 88 respondents from different parts of the world through online distribution.

Data gathering for Section II

In the second section of the questionnaire had a total of 5 questions before the respondents, and they were required to tick the given numbers 1-4 in order to showcase their level of agreement or disagreement on each of the question. This section stands to answer this research question, ” **Are there constraints and keys to a successful deployment of the different retail technologies?** Analyzing the five questions in this section that answers this research question, which are:

Q6: Do you agree that shopping has been made easier as a direct consequence of retail technologies introduced by Walmart?

There were just 3.4% who strongly disagree and 2.3% slightly disagree which is a total of 5.7% who disagree, while 67% strongly agree and 27.3% slightly agree which is a total of 94.3% who agree.

The second question is

Q7: Do you agree that the experience has been fulfilling and seamless?

There were just 2.2% who strongly disagree and 0% slightly disagree which is a total of 2.2% who disagree, while 48.9% strongly agree and 48.9% slightly agree which is a total of 97.8% who agree.

The third question is;

Q8: Do you agree that retail technologies introduced by Walmart had little or no constraints?

There were just 5.7% who strongly disagree and 8% slightly disagree which is a total of 13.7% who disagree, while 34% strongly agree and 52.3% slightly agree which is a total of 86.3% who agree.

The fourth question

Q9: Do you agree that retail technologies deployment is key to the overall success of retail industries?

There were just 1.1% who strongly disagree and 1.1% slightly disagree which is a total of 2.2% who disagree while 53.4% strongly agree and 44.3% slightly agree which is a total of 97.7% who agree.

Q10: Do you agree that retail industries should be encouraged to deploy different types of retail technology for the enhancement of their business and customer satisfaction?

There were just 1.1% who strongly disagree and 1.1% slightly disagree which is a total of 2.2% who disagree while 76.1% strongly agree and 21.6% slightly agree which is a total of 97.7% who agree.

Findings in this section II can be viewed on the bar chart below

Data gathering for Section III

Q11: Do you agree that constraint(s) you may have noticed is not commensurate to that of manual application?

There were just 5.7% who strongly disagree and 4.5% slightly disagree which is a total of 10.2% who disagree, while 40.9% strongly agree and 48.9% slightly agree which is a total of 88.8% who agree.

Q12: Do you agree that company’s goals, staff needs and customer satisfaction can be achieved faster using technology rather than manual methods of retail, regardless of deployment constraints?

There were just 3.4% who strongly disagree and 3.4% slightly disagree which is a total of 6.8% who disagree, while 62.5% strongly agree and 30.7% slightly agree which is a total of 93.2% who agree.

Q13: Do you agree that technology brings about high performance in the retail industry both to customers, staff and company?

There were just 2.2% who strongly disagree and 2.2% slightly disagree which is a total of 4.4% who disagree, while 70.5% strongly agree and 25% slightly agree which is a total of 95.5% who agree.

Q14: Do you agree that deployment of technology in a retail company improves the performance of their staff?

There were just 2.4% who strongly disagree and 4.5% slightly disagree which is a total of 6.9% who disagree, while 54.5% strongly agree and 38.6% slightly agree which is a total of 93.1% who agree.

Q15: Do you agree that technology effectively brings about faster service delivery?

There were just 1.2% who strongly disagree and 3.4% slightly disagree which is a total 4.6% who disagree, while 69.3% strongly agree and 26.1% slightly agree which is a total of 95.4% who agree.

Q16: Do you agree that the deployment of retail technology closes the gap in logistics?

There were just 2.3% who strongly disagree and 6.8% slightly disagree which is a total 9.1% who disagree, while 46.6% strongly agree and 44.3% slightly agree which is a total of 90.9% who agree.

Q17. Do you agree that a retail company can only meet up and surpass its organizational goals in modern times only if it deploys different retail technologies in order to meet up with the industry's pace?

There were just 1.1% who strongly disagree and 3.4% slightly disagree which is a total 4.5% who disagree, while 59.1% strongly agree and 36.4% slightly agree which is a total of 95.5% who agree.

Q18: Do you agree that technology in retail industry enhances the human resource management of the company?

There were just 2.2% who strongly disagree and 3.4% slightly disagree which is a total 5.6% who disagree, while 58% strongly agree and 36.4% slightly agree which is a total of 95.5% who agree.

Q19: Do you agree that a deployment of retail technology attracts more customers as well as keeps them due to efficiency?

There were just 3.4% who strongly disagree and 4.5% slightly disagree which is a total 7.9% who disagree, while 58% strongly agree and 34.1% slightly agree which is a total of 92.1% who agree.

Q20: Do you agree that Walmart services to customers have significantly improved since the deployment of some retail applications, which has enhanced faster service delivery?

There were just 3.4% who strongly disagree and 3.4% slightly disagree which is a total 6.8% who disagree, while 59% strongly agree and 34.1% slightly agree which is a total of 93.2% who agree.

Findings for section III can be viewed at a glance below;

3.6 Justification For the Use of Quantitative Approach

The essence of this study is to establish the impact of technology on the supply chain management. This can be done only by the use of quantitative research approach which is the process of collecting and analyzing data in order to find patterns, make futuristic predictions, test sample population and use it to generalize the findings to a wider population. Quantitative approach is the best for this study because in order to ascertain the facts behind this statement, primary and secondary data need to be collected, analyzed and interpreted from life experiences as well as review the different technologies applied to supply chain of the case study company in order to showcase the effectiveness of such deployment as well as constraints encountered in the deployment and the keys to a successful deployment then use the findings for future predictions and recommendations for improvement on the achievement of the set goal of the company.

Sample data we get from live data quantifies the reliability on this method of research. The crux of this quantitative approach is the principle of objectivity. The instruments that are used to obtain data for this study are statistical methods, and researcher's own intervention needs to be objective. Objectivity in research methods and approach increases the likelihood that conclusions would be objective in nature and so reliable. That's why the choice of quantitative research approach because the questions are closed-ended then the findings will be objective.

CHAPTER 4 - RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Calculation of Result

Based on the data gathered, some results are analyzed in order to get the figures and graphical representation of the survey results that will clearly demonstrate the outcome of the survey without ambiguity. Data was collected individually and collectively for the purposes of answering the research questions from the calculated, analyzed, and interpreted as well as test the hypothesis. In calculating the result, the research questions have to be considered so that the result can be used to answer the question as follows;

- I. Are there constraints and keys to a successful deployment of the different retail technologies?
- II. Does technology positively impact on the customers and employee satisfaction as well as achievement of set goal?

In that regard all the results of the survey included in the second section are put together, and it was found that in a bid to respond to the five questions of the section II which answers research question 1.

1. Are there constraints and keys to a successful deployment of different retail technologies?

There were 246 (55.9%) responses recorded for strongly agree, 171 (38.9%) for slightly agree, 12 (2.7%) for strongly disagree and 11 (2.5%) for slightly disagree. Hence, it is found that while responding to the questions of the section II, a total of 94.8% of the people agreed while 5.2% disagreed. This means that there are insignificant constraints on the successful deployment and key or device for achieving a successful deployment of technological applications to the supply chain management processes of a company. The results obtained from section II of the questionnaire are shown with the help of following pie chart,

And in a bid to answer the second research question which is, **‘does technology positively impact on the customers and staff satisfaction as well as achievement of set goal?’**

Section III questions were populated, and here are the findings to buttress the statement in the affirmative. Ten questions of the section III had 509(57.8 percent) responses recorded for strongly agree, 312(35.5 percent) for slightly agree, 26(3.0 percent) for strongly disagree and 33(3.8%) for slightly disagree. Hence, it was found that while responding to the questions of the section III, a total of 92.2% agreed that technology deployment impacts positively on the supply chain management of a company. The results obtained from section III of the questionnaire are shown with the help of following pie chart

4.1.2 Overview of the survey result

The results presented by the sections are also combined in order to get the overall results of the survey, and it was found that there were a total 20 questions through three different sections and on these 20 questions, there were 88 respondents who expressed their opinions, out of which 755 responses were strongly agree, 483 were slightly agree, 38 were strongly disagree while 44 responses were slightly disagree which represents a total number of responses to 1320. Hence, it is revealed from the combined results of the survey that there are 57.2 percent of the respondents strongly agree with the positive impact of technology on retail businesses, 36.6 percent are slightly agree, 2.9 percent strongly disagree while 3.3 percent slightly disagree with all the statements that reflect the strong positive impact of technology on retail businesses and their performance.

The combined results of the survey can be viewed in the following chart.

By analysis, strongly agree and slightly agree are categorized as one while strongly disagree and slightly disagree are also one, hence the following analysis,

Total number of strongly agree and slightly agree is $755 + 483$ equal to 1238 representing 93.7 percent of the total responses of 1320 while strongly disagree and slightly disagree is $38 + 44$ which is equal to 82 representing 6.2 percent of the total responses of 1320. The pie chart below is used to depict the strong positive impact of technology on the performance of retail businesses vis a viz the satisfaction of customers and staff,

4.1.3 Display of survey result

Table 4.1 combined results of the survey

Section	Strongly agree	Slightly agree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly agree
Section II	246	171	26	12
Section III	509	312	33	11
Total	755	483	59	23
Percentage	57.3	36.6	4.4	1.7

Fig 4.1 analysis of survey research result showing the impact

Fig 4.2 overall positive impact of technology

The results are calculated separately and jointly and represented as such with bar chart and pie chart for clearer understanding of the result of the survey which will be used for the analysis; answer the research questions and hypotheses.

4.2 Analysis and Interpretation of Primary Data

The findings of the survey threw light on the research questions

- I. Are there constraints and keys to a successful deployment of the different retail technologies?
- II. Does technology positively impact on the customers and staff satisfaction as well as achievement of set goal?

Seeking to give a precise and accurate justification for the answer. This opened up issues related to those questions in a bid to answer it properly. It's clear that from the result that a large percentage of consumers, company owners and employees strongly agree that there is huge positive impact on the deployment of technologies on retail businesses and so there is growing importance in embracing technologies by retail industries as the way of sure business growth in terms of customer and staff satisfaction as well as faster company's achievement of set goals.

The questionnaire was done with positivism which makes it easy to see that the strongly agreed responses reveal the general acceptance of the statement that there is obvious positive impact on retail business with the deployment of technologies in the business of retail industries.

How the sections were presented on the questionnaire for the survey shows great concern towards

different issues to expose the trend of business with the application of technologies.

The analysis of section I and section III shows that generally there is an accepted fact that technology is the only sure way of engaging in retail businesses and be sure of reaching your goal with ease with improved customer service, logistics, supply chain and improved revenue generation which brings about significant impact on the retail industries. The questions showcased on section II were all focused on constraints and successful deployment of retail technologies using Walmart as a case study and its positive impact on the performance of the business and as it was discovered that 55.9 percent of the respondents strongly agreed while 38.9 percent slightly agree with the statements. This means that both the employee, consumers and business owners agrees that deployment of technologies on retail outfit brings about seamless transactions which improve service delivery without disrupting flow of transactions. This confirms that the stakeholders all feel good with the deployment having noticed little or no constraints in the deployment, rather see only successful flow of transactions. There are just 2.7 percent and 2.5 percent of the respondents who strongly disagree and slightly disagree with the given statements, which shows that insignificant number are yet to feel the impact.

Analysis of the findings on section III shows that a good number of people from different works of life all over the world have accepted that technology makes the huge difference needed to turn around retail businesses for better performance towards actualization of set goals, customer satisfaction and staff satisfaction and so are of the opinion that it has become inevitable with the significant positive impact it portends. It was revealed that 57.7 percent and 35.5 percent strongly agree and slightly agree respectively with the positive impact of technology on retail businesses while 3 percent strongly disagree and 3.8 slightly disagree with the statement and these numbers represent an insignificant number which means there huge percentage of men and women from all walks of life across the globe who strongly affirms to the statement given their lives experiences.

This result confirms the work of Prashant, (2010) quoted in the literature review. He declared the importance of information technology in supply chain management. His work pinpoints the roles of information technology on the supply chain as service delivery and improved efficiency. This is in tandem with the results herein: in essence, this dissertation provides empirical proof of Prashant's hypothesis. Furthermore, this dissertation complements the work of Sanjay (2012) who recognized that management and human resources practices are as integral part of an organization which leads to the satisfactory performance of a company's supply chain management, employee well-being and derive recommendations. The leeward side of his work creates a gap, as not only does it not identify a performance index, it also ignores the role of customers in determining what could be called a

satisfactory supply chain. In complementing his work, this dissertation suggests that looking at the customers (and indeed it did) for insight into the answers of if technology could improve a supply chain or the benchmark level of efficiency that a deployment of technology should obtain.

Nguyen (2017) had his analysis drawn from Walmart related literature; he postulated that a redesign of a supply chain would enable the organization to be more flexible and efficient. His research did not fit the role of a general picture that bares a solution to an inefficient supply chain.

The results of the questionnaire and Walmart's annual report, we decipher that the integration of advanced technology into its already existing supply chain structure enabled Walmart's rapid growth. Rather than identifying efficiency as just an index, the results highlight the need to access a supply chain from the view of the customers. The customers are the recipients of the service and should have a stakeholder's input.

The works of Grunesken et al (2017) further buttresses this point by acknowledging big data gotten from customers as a means of achieving business value. These values are enshrined in the ideal state of a retail organization.

On another stream of consciousness, understanding or identifying the drawn line between excessive or inordinate deployment of technology and the appropriate one is equally important as knowing what technology to deploy. As explained by Faroudi et al. (2017), customers are more satisfied with technology deployment but can identify a deployment without a human face: technology deployed for a reduction in retail cost than for improved customer service delivery. This same conclusion can be deduced from the results of section II in the questionnaire herein this research.

A final facet of this analysis is the constraint from the response to question 8 of the questionnaire. It revealed the fact that customers noticed the constraints to the deployment of technology ongoing at Walmart. As noted by Slat-wall (2015), calibrating a technology to satisfy customers may come with several 'stops', 'pull-outs', 'reinventing' or 're-innovating', and replug of technology into the retail business. Walmart was no exception, as revealed by the results of question 7 of and supported by results from question 8.

This study in analyzing fig 2.7.2 which shows how technology positively impacted sales revenue of 10 top ranked companies showing the progression using Walmart as a case study, fig 2.7.2 shows a literature review done by retail ecommerce (EMarketer 2020 which shows the progress of these companies using technology that fits their supply chain and the following were deduce;

1. That in 2017,% of total retail ecommerce sales of Amazon increased exponentially 42%,2018 it was 44% while 2019 was 47%.
2. Ebay ranked second according to this review,it had a declining growth because of non technological push as required by the global trend 2017,2018,2019 with declining percentages of 7.6%,6.8% and 6.1% respectively
3. Walmart which ranked 3rd had growth in their global sales revenue as follows 2017(3.3%) 2018(4%) 2019 had 4.6% growth as a result of technological innovations which Walmart is known for.

In fig 2.7 Walmart became world largest retailer by Statista 2020 reported by Kantar (March/April,2020), Walmart overtook Amazon(just by deployment of technological innovations) with a huge margin of ecommerce sales revenue of \$527.8b while Amazon was at \$268.2b as shown above. This review and findings goes to support the statement having been confirmed by the findings of this study section II and III

4.3 Discussing the arising issues from the research

4.3.1 Answering the Research Questions

This study was carried out with the aim of finding answers to the raised research questions on the methodology and having gone through life surveys and have received responses now we can use the findings to answer the questions as follows,

- I. Are there constraints and keys to a successful deployment of the different retail technologies?
- II. Does technology positively impact on the customers and staff satisfaction as well as achievement of set goal?

In the construction of the questionnaires, the first research questions,” Do you agree that there are little or no constraints to successful deployment of the different retail technologies?” was put into considerations in order to bring out the answer from the responses and so section II responses to the five questions clearly answers that question in the affirmative with the responses being that 55.9 percent strongly agree and 38.9 percent slightly agree which clearly indicate that a significant combination of 94.8 percent agree that indeed there are little or no constraints to a successful

deployment of different retail technologies because from their responses the transactions were seamless with faster service delivery without noticeable hitches rather free flow of transactions as such the first research question for the purposes of this study has been answered cleared by section II without the graphical representation for better understanding.

The second research question was, ” **Does technology positively impact on the customers and staff satisfaction as well as achievement of set goal?**

In order to get accurate opinion and life experiences of the respondents, answer to this question was considered when the questions that were presented to the respondents in section III were constructed and so the analysis of this findings will expressly answer this question and having analyzed the survey result, it was discovered that 57.7 + 35.5 percent respondents(93.2%) agree while 3+3.8 percent(6.8%) disagree with the statement that there is significant positive impact on the application of technology on supply chain management and logistics of retail industries. This however indicates that a huge number of respondents from experience confirm the statement, which then answers the second research question.

Given the above analysis, it is obvious that all the research questions have been answered with clarity with the help of the data gathered through the survey, the overall positive responses as shown in the analysis on Table 4.1,figure 4.1 and fig 4.2 confirming that there is positive impact of positive impact on the application of technology on supply chain management of retail industries having proved this with live experiences.

CHAPTER 5 - CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Hypotheses Testing

It's very important to test the hypothesis of this survey and this is only possible after gathering the results of the survey which is needed for this test. The first research hypothesis is "Using Walmart as a case study to ascertain the true position of the research statement" This hypothesis is not only proved to be useful through this primary source-survey but also through the secondary sources which confirms that Walmart the big giant lost swiftly to Amazon just because of non-application of trending technology and only got back its position as soon as it launched various retail technologies deployment which their consumers experienced and reported on the survey and also the review of secondary data revealed that Walmart as a global giant in retail industry provided unprecedented data which was analyzed for the benefit of confirming this research statement and so this first hypothesis is tested and verified by the result of this study,

The second research hypothesis is" Using female and male consumers, business owners and employees with their age bracket considered in order to show serious shoppers who understands the use of technology in the services' delivery they require as well as understand consumer needs and expectations "This hypothesis was also verified by this primary data which shows that the respondents were 58% above 40,26.1% 30–40 years of age, 20–30 years of age(just 8%) while below 20 years of age were just 8% too and also female shoppers (71.6%) while male respondents were (28.5%) This again shows good data collection having been proven that female shop more in retail shops than mean and so the data presented and reviewed depicts a true representation of reality. Also, secondary data as seen in this research review has data gathering from responsible reviews from Walmart itself and other reliable retail industries' analyst. Therefore, this second hypothesis is tested and verified.

The third hypothesis is," The use of online distribution of questionnaire to gather data from shoppers who shop frequently and are across the globe" so it's not restricted to a particular geopolitical location or just shoppers that shop once in a long time instead the respondents cut across countries like USA 43.3%, EUROPE 4.5%, Canada 19.3%, others 31.8% as well as shop weekly 37.5%, monthly 20.5%, quarterly 39.8% which indicates that they are frequent buyers who will easily notice any positive impact if there is. This also was tested and verified from the results gathered from this primary source as well as secondary data review. It was found that data collected using these types of consumers represents clearly the reality on the ground.

Going by what several researches said about the authenticity of data collected online as well as secondary data gathered by reliable institution that by using the outcome of consumer research

companies can and have made tremendous improvement in the growth of their businesses and then this research can be said to have met every standard for reliability

Having confirmed that due to the deployment of retail technologies by Walmart that consumers witnessed and are still witnessing improvement in service delivery which brings about customer satisfaction which increases the number of repeat buy which will in turn increase company revenue and profitability while reducing cost which ultimately means having significant positive impact on supply chain management and logistics of retail industries

5.1 Analysis and Discussion

The study surveys different areas of application of technology in retail industries and its impact on their customers, employees and general achievement of company's set goals. With the help of literature review and statistical survey among shoppers of Walmart across the globe, the results of the survey shows that effective deployment of technology in retail industries is a necessary tool for the growth of retail businesses as displays by Walmart resilience in sustaining its position as the giant of retail industries given the stiff competition.

In order to survive in the highly competitive marketplace, the companies are therefore expected to adopt application of technology and so retail industries' in their different sizes can only achieve their desired growth in the face of stiff competition given the sorry state the pandemic has put the global economy into, technology therefore becomes the only answer to survival in the face of high use of technology by a lot of shoppers who would rather have it very easy shopping seamlessly and so as far as retail businesses are concerned this study revealed that the only acceptable approach to the achieving total success in retail business is by complete embrace of the deployment of effective technological applications in the supply chain management process of a retail industry because it is crucial for the business organizations that they follow the technological trend in the ever-changing approach of doing business in the world.

The study also confirms that technology adds to the profitability of the organizations, customer and employee satisfaction. The consumer research conducted through internet act as an important tool for the companies in formulating their supply chain management process in order to be assured of the high profitability required by the companies. Consumers generally have recognized the positive impact of the effective deployment of technology in retail industries irrespective of the size that way there will be positive and favorable response and reaction by the public which will in turn mean increase in revenue and subsequent increase in profit while reducing cost to the barest minimum.

5.2 Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, even though this study had some challenges in the gathering of data because of the current pandemic situation, Walmart as a retail giant has enough reviews from strong accredited review companies whose data can be relied upon and also the 88 questionnaire respondents from across the globe represented diversity in the research from shoppers without physical interface gave their sincere responses from their recent shopping experiences after the deployment of some technologies to the supply chain management of the case study company Walmart and so the conclusion here can be relied upon.

After analyzing the findings of this study, it expressly established beyond every reasonable doubt that technology significantly impacts positively on supply chain management of a retail industry by increasing the customers and employee satisfaction as well as the achievement of the set objective of the company if deployed effectively and efficiently as proved by this study. Some research in the past had iterated the same notion of technology impacting positively on a retail organisations supply chain as well as on the improved services rendered to customers. To prove this hypothesis, quantitatively, the researchers have utilized several research methods. The ideals behind these research was on other premises alien from a customer's perspectives. This dissertation used customers perspective to make a reliable inference being that they represent unbiased population that's capable of producing result that can be relied on for future decisions on a better approach to use in order to remain in business competitively being that they determine the success of every retail organization which further fills the gap previous researchers left. The findings which used Walmart as a case study was able to prove that they have been able to maintain their position as giant retailer only by effective deployment of relevant technologies to their supply chain management which ultimately led to high performance in their sales revenue while lowering cost. These have been used consistently by Walmart over the year and has made their competitors go after their formidable strategy, which this study clearly showed when the used technological innovations to take over the lead worldwide from Amazon.

However, the main factors responsible for the success experienced by Walmart in their customer satisfaction and high performance in sales revenue have been highlighted as mainly the effective deployment of different technologies in the supply chain management. Walmart has therefore carved a niche for itself as the leader in supply chain in the retail industry and has remained the envy of others.

During this Pandemic, Walmart has been able to use technology deployed to different areas of its business to display strength and remain highly competitive in the face of uncertainties that faced retail

businesses way of doing business but Walmart net worth skyrocketed as shown the statistics in fig 3 where he took the lead among other retailers and even above Amazon as number one retailer in the world with a very wide margin using technological deployment to achieve this. Having seen the impact of Technology, Walmart has positioned itself as a leader in supply chain with the help of technological innovations.

Empirical data analysis derived from the questionnaires and the quantitative statistical review done by reliable companies has proved that there is significant positive impact on customers and employee satisfaction as well as significant increase in the actualization of set goals by retail industries as a result of deployment of technologies to their supply chain management processes as evidenced in Walmart review. The results of this study have expressly provided solution to the attainment of the research objectives of this study, as stated thus;

- III. To explain the different technologies deployed by Walmart in solving its supply Chain management problems, considering its constraints and strength.
- IV. To Analyze how a deployment of retail industry's cutting edge technology could impact positively on a retail organization's supply chain and by extension recommend possible methods of reorganization to accommodate a successful deployment of retail technology.

These objectives have been thoroughly dealt with in this research and the analysis strongly showing that even though there is no significant constraint noticed by the shoppers as shown in the seamless transactions, companies need to be mindful of deploying technology that perfectly suit their need in order to get the desired positive outcome. With the analysis cutting edge technology is the only sure answer to a positive impact to the supply chain management of a retail company and so should be embraced by any retail company that want to remain competitive giving the ever-changing need of customers.

5.3 Recommendations

On the basis of the above conclusion on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are given;

- An effective deployment of technology to retail organization supply chain management as a tool to improving customer service delivery is necessary.
- Retail companies should always swiftly embrace emerging technology to replace existing one

as technologies tend to go obsolete fast with the emergence of new one that is capable of bridging the gap found in the existing one as such strong IT department is highly recommended in order to always advice on the new trend of technology for better result in line with the company's set objectives

- In the face of the uncertainties that challenge the retail industries shown in the recent hit by pandemic Covid-19 where retail businesses were affected tremendously suddenly, retail industries should take approach towards positioning themselves very well in the digital ecommerce world in order to take advantage of new technologies as they evolve.
- Given the current trend, it's good for retail industries to be mindful of a good fit for any technological solution they want to deploy.
- Continuous improvement in their way of doing business is very necessary and so technological innovations are highly recommended in the face of competition.
- Cost of deployment should be considered as this study has shown that a good fit is not necessarily how expensive but how effectively fitted it is.
- Emphasis on employee satisfaction is key while considering which technology to use such that will be easily understood and managed by employees for efficiency.
- Training is very important among employees and employers in order to achieve the desired result from the deployed technology.

5.3.1 Recommendation for Further Studies

The outcome of this study was limited to the few respondents and reviews of some companies, this creates an avenue for further study to be conducted which will involve larger sample population and usage of other retail companies as case study in order to delve more into different areas of constraints while deploying the technological tools and also reach out to employees to further analyze the impact of technology on the supply chain of retail organizations as this findings if utilized will improve entrepreneurship which will ultimately translate into improvement of sales revenue in different retail outfit whether small or big in the long run.

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APPENDIX

The Questionnaire

This survey seeks to answer the following research questions for the purposes of proving the statement that there is significant positive impact of the deployment of retail technologies on the customers' staff and organizational goal;

- I. Are there constraints and keys to a successful deployment of the different retail technologies?**
- II. Does technology positively impact on the customers and staff satisfaction as well as achievement of set goal?**

Section I – Information about Respondents:

Age bracket

Gender

Location

Employment type:

Q5 How often do you shop at Walmart?

Section II – Information about the case study company-Walmart and the successful deployment of the different retail technologies

These questions answer the first research question

(1. = Strongly Agree 2. = Slightly Agree 3. = Strongly Disagree 4. = Strongly Disagree.)

- Q6 Do you agree that shopping has been made easier as a direct consequence of retail technologies introduced by Walmart?
- Q7 Do you agree that the experience has been fulfilling and seamless?
- Q8 Do you agree that retail technologies introduced by Walmart had little or no constraints?

- Q9 Do you agree that retail technologies deployment is key to the overall success of retail industries?
- Q10 Do you agree that retail industries should be encouraged to deploy different types of retail technology for the enhancement of their business and customer satisfaction?

Section III- Information about the positive impact of the deployed retail technologies by Walmart on costumers and staff as well as company's achievement of goals. These responses answer the second research question.

(1. = Strongly Agree 2. = Slightly Agree 3. = Strongly Disagree 4. = Strongly Disagree.)

- Q11 Do you agree that constraint(s) you may have noticed is not commensurate to that of manual application?
- Q12 Do you agree that company's goals, staff needs and customer satisfaction can be achieved faster using technology rather than manual methods of retail regardless of deployment constraints?
- Q13 Do you agree that technology brings about high performance in the retail industry both to customers, staff and company?
- Q14 Do you agree that deployment of technology in a retail company improves the performance of their staff?
- Q15 Do you agree that technology effectively brings about faster service delivery? Strongly Agree
- Q16 Do you agree that the deployment of retail technology closes the gap in logistics?
- Q17 Do you agree that a retail company can only meet up and surpass its organizational goals in modern times only if it deploys different retail technologies in order to meet up with the industry's pace ?
- Q18 Do you agree that technology in retail industry enhances the human resource management of the company?
- Q19 Do you agree that a deployment of retail technology attracts more customers as well as keeps them due to efficiency?

Q20 Do you agree that Walmart services to customers have significantly improved since the deployment of some retail applications which has enhanced faster service delivery?

Survey Responses.

Q1 Your age bracket*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice

Total

Below 20	7
20-30	7
30-40	23
Above 40	51

Q2 Your Gender*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Male	25
Female	63
Rather not Say	0

Q3 Location*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
United States of America	28
Europe	4
Canada	17

Others

39

Q4 Employment

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Business Owner	9
Employee	48
Self Employed	17
Others	14

Q5 How often do you shop at Walmart?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Daily	2
Weekly	33
Monthly	18
Quarterly	35

Q6 Do you agree that shopping has been made easier as a direct consequence of retail technologies

introduced by Walmart?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice

Total

Strongly agree	59
slightly Agree	24
Strongly Disagree	3
Slightly Disagree	2

Q7 Do you agree that the experience has been fulfilling and seamless?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	43
Slightly Agree	43
Strongly Disagree	2
Slightly Disagree	0

Q8 Do you agree that retail technologies introduced by Walmart had little or no constraints?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	30
Slightly Agree	46
Strongly Disagree	5
Slightly Disagree	7

Q9 Do you agree that retail technologies deployment is key to the overall success of retail industries?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	47
Slightly Agree	39
Strongly Disagree	1
Slightly Disagree	1

Q10 Do you agree that retail industries should be encouraged to deploy different types of retail technology for the enhancement of their business and customer satisfaction?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	67
lightly Agree	19
Strongly Disagree	1
Slightly Disagree	1

Q11 Do you agree that constraint(s) you may have noticed is not commensurate to that of manual application?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	36
Slightly Agree	43
Strongly Disagree	5
Slightly Disagree	4

Q12 Do you agree that company's goals, staff needs and customer satisfaction can be achieved faster using technology rather than manual methods of retail regardless of deployment constraints?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	55
Slightly Agree	27
Strongly Disagree	3

Slightly Disagree

3

Q13 Do you agree that technology brings about high performance in the retail industry both to customers, staff and company?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice

Total

Strongly Agree

62

Slightly Agree	22
Strongly Disagree	2
Slightly Disagree	2

Q14 Do you agree that deployment of technology in a retail company improves the performance of their staff?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	48
Slightly Agree	34
Strongly Disagree	2
Slightly Disagree	4

Q15 Do you agree that technology effectively brings about faster service delivery?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	61
Slightly Agree	23
Strongly Disagree	1
Slightly Disagree	3

Q16 Do you agree that the deployment of retail technology closes the gap in logistics?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	41
Slightly Agree	39
Strongly Disagree	2
Slightly Disagree	6

Q17 Do you agree that a retail company can only meet up and surpass its organizational goals in modern times only if it deploys different retail technologies in order to meet up with the industry's pace ?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	52
Slightly Agree	32
Strongly Disagree	3

Slightly Disagree

1

Q18 Do you agree that technology in retail industry enhances the human resource management of the company?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	51
Slightly Agree	32
Strongly Disagree	2
Slightly Disagree	3

Q19 Do you agree that a deployment of retail technology attracts more customers as well as keeps them due to efficiency?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	51
Slightly Agree	30
Strongly Disagree	3
Slightly Disagree	4

Q20 Do you agree that Walmart services to customers have significantly improved since the deployment of some retail applications which has enhanced faster service delivery?*

Answered: 88 Unanswered: 0

Choice	Total
Strongly Agree	52
Slightly Agree	30
Strongly Disagree	3
Slightly Disagree	3

Other Graphs

Consumer Affairs

Overview

Walmart has a consumer rating of **3.47 stars** from 4,184 reviews indicating that most customers are generally satisfied with their purchases. Consumers satisfied with Walmart most frequently mention free shipping, great prices and local store. Walmart ranks **14th** among Discount Shopping sites.

Service	★★★★☆	200
Value	★★★★☆	192
Shipping	★★★★☆	167
Returns	★★★★☆	144

Reviews (4,184)

Sort by: **Relevant** ▼

Rating

Timeframe

All time ▼

Other

- Verified purchase
- Contains image or video
- English only

Reviews that mention popular keywords

customer service (439)

credit card (76)

gift card (0)

delivery date (39)

store manager (0)

bank account (0)

return policy (40)

shopping experience (35)

55,508 English reviews out of 58,982

Sort Popular

3.3 ★★★★★ ▼

Recommend to a Friend

Approve of CEO

Doug McMillon
16,175 Ratings

Pros

- "Flexible schedule with good pay" (in 2723 reviews)
- "Good benefits when you become full-time" (in 1443 reviews)
- "Flexible hours decent pay and hour lunch" (in 1126 reviews)
- "Flexible hours for all students" (in 1094 reviews)
- "Great working conditions great people" (in 1015 reviews)

Cons

- "you endure standing for long hours" (in 1598 reviews)
- "long hours reduce work-life balance" (in 1218 reviews)
- "Lack of communication with upper management" (in 923 reviews)
- "sometimes there is poor management" (in 725 reviews)

Glass Door

